

Simulation and experimental validation of pulsating heat pipes

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Abstract: The one-dimensional transient numerical code of JJ Cooling Innovation has been significantly improved to simulate the thermal/hydraulic performance of pulsating heat pipes (PHPs). Using a mechanistic approach, the liquid slug and vapor plug flows and their interaction with the surrounding wall are modeled. The heat transfer is predicted using the Three-Zone Model of flow boiling in microchannels, which includes liquid film evaporation and liquid film condensation of vapor plugs and convection of liquid slugs. Discretizing the entire PHP serpentine into one continuous grid, the code solves all variables based on local conditions. The code allows the user to define the working fluid, the channel's shape, material and wall roughness, the serpentine's pitch, the geometrical parameters of evaporator, adiabatic region and condenser zones, and the operating parameters. The boundary conditions in the evaporator zone can either be constant heat flux or constant temperature, while on the condenser side, the coolant temperature is constant as well as the heat transfer coefficient. The code works without any fitting factor and predicts all local variables in the 1D grid as a function of time, including the liquid film thickness and the onset of boiling for the formation of new vapor plugs within the evaporating and adiabatic zones, if local nucleation conditions are reached. Growth, collapse and coalescence of generated bubbles are taken into account. The film thermal resistance is corrected to a radial conduction model. The implementation of the initial liquid film thickness laid behind a liquid slug is updated to include the effect of the bubble velocity and acceleration as well as the length of the leading slug. The nucleation of new vapor plug has also been updated. The onset of nucleation is only dependent on the local thermodynamic state. If the threshold is reached, a new method is used to simulate micro-bubbles formation and coalescence to a channel-size vapor plug. These modifications greatly improve the code accuracy and stability allowing simulations with high pressure fluid rather than ethanol only. Furthermore, in the on-going EU project *Pulsating Heat Pipes for Hybrid Propulsion Systems (PHP2)*, a new PHP test bench has been designed and built at Provides Metalmeccanica. A copper tube PHP with a 19-turn of 2.0mm internal diameter and 12mm tube pitch was tested over a wide range of imposed heat loads. A microchannel water-cooling plate was used at the condenser side with an inlet temperature of 20°C. Then, tests were done for vertical and horizontal orientations with R1233zd(E) as the working fluid. The code, which was previously validated for ethanol PHP test data from KAIST, is now successfully validated for the present experimental data points. Accurate results were obtained from low heat loads up to 250W for a set of 49 data points, predicting 97% within an error bandwidth of 30%.

Keywords:

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[Nomenclature]

a	bubble acceleration [m/s^2]
A_{CS}	cross sectional area [m^2]
Bo	bond number [-]
Bo_a	acceleration Bond number [-]
Ca	capillary number [-]
c	specific heat [J/kgK]
D	diameter [m]
F_{PR}	pressure correction factor [-]
h	heat transfer coefficient [W/m^2K]
i_{lv}	latent heat of vaporization [J/kg]
k	thermal conductivity [W/mK]
L	length [m]
m'	mass per unit of length [kg/m]
n	Gorenflo's pressure correction exponent [-]
N	number of element
P	pressure [Pa]
p^*	reduced pressure [-]
p_f	working fluid property ratio [-]
q	heat flux [W/m^2]
q'	linear heat flux over the perimeter [W/m]
R	thermal resistance [K/W]
R'	thermal resistance per unit length [$m.K/W$]
Ra	mean surface roughness [m]
Re	Reynolds number [-]
T	temperature [K]
t	wall thickness [m]
U	velocity of the leading meniscus [m/s]
W	PHP width [m]

[Greek Symbol]

δ	film thickness [m]
δ_0	initial film thickness [m]
ρ	density [kg/m^3]
σ	surface tension [N/m]

[Subscript]

0	reference
<i>a</i>	adiabatic
<i>c</i>	condenser
<i>cool</i>	coolant of the condenser, water
<i>e</i>	evaporator
<i>f</i>	film
<i>i</i>	inner
<i>l</i>	liquid phase
<i>nb</i>	nucleate boiling
<i>o</i>	outer
<i>sat</i>	saturated state
<i>tot</i>	total, cumulative
<i>v</i>	vapor phase
<i>vbl</i>	viscous boundary layer
<i>w</i>	wall

1. Introduction

Electronics components such as CPUs and IGBT modules are exponentially increasing their footprint heat flux as they are becoming more compact. Air-cooled heat spreaders (even with integrated heat pipes) are no longer an option for cooling of the newest high power dissipating components. Thus, passive cooling technology is seen as a new viable solution with particular attention here to pulsating heat pipes (PHP). It is a very compact cooling element (either a tubular serpentine or a flat plate serpentine) which operates in a chaotic, but predictable, behaviour of two-phase flow guaranteeing high heat transfer performance under negligible values of energy consumption (energy is still needed to pump the secondary fluid to remove the heat from the condenser end of the PHP). Thus, a high performance PHP can be considered to be a very high thermal conductive and capacity plate with good thermal characteristics both into its thin thickness and along its length.

Akachi [1] is usually credited for originally proposing PHPs, defined as small size channels spanning back and forth between an evaporator section and a condenser section. The PHP transports the heat from the evaporator to the condenser through self-instigated and self-sustaining oscillations of slug and plug flows. The operating fluid and filling ratio are adjusted to improve the oscillations and consequently the heat transfer rate from the evaporator. The driving forces acting in a PHP passive system come from the nucleation and collapse of vapor plugs in the evaporator and condenser sections, respectively.

Despite the relevance of this new and highly promising technology, the number of experimental investigations that can be found in the open literature is not representative and conclusive. Studies have been performed to analyze the effect of geometrical parameters, such as channel geometry [2–4], PHP configuration (close-end or close-loop) [5], and number of turns [5–7]. Additionally, some analyses were performed to evaluate the effects of parameters such as the type of working fluid [8,9], PHP orientation [5,7] and filling ratio [10]. It is worth to mention that the PHP internal flow pattern can be characterized as: intermittent oscillatory flow, stable oscillations, and circulation flow [11,12], which depends on the geometrical and operational parameters. Other studies presented experimental data with a modified PHP in an attempt to enforce the circulation mode [13,14]. Most of this experimental work has been summarized in two recent book chapters [15,16].

Several numerical models have been developed. Inside their study Noh and Kim [17] reviewed these previous works and classified them according to their film dynamic model. Mameli et al. [18] used a constant film thickness along the whole vapor plug to calculate an equivalent local vapor quality used together with the flow boiling heat transfer coefficient from Gungor-Winterton. They have shown that the local pressure drop in the bend has a non-negligible effect on the PHP performance. Using a constant film thickness model as well, Manzoni et al. [19,20] have simulated PHPs under transient reduced gravity and obtained accurate results compared to their experimental data. Nikolayev et al. have developed one of the first simulation code using a constant film thickness, they improved their model especially with an implementation of the heat conduction in the PHP walls and bubble generation [21,22]. Senjaya and Inoue [23] presented a numerical model integrating the possibility for new vapor plugs to nucleate. The location of the nucleation was fixed as well as the nucleation threshold. In their simulations, the PHP heat transfer rate increases considerably when using the new bubble generation model. The recent study from Bae et al. [24], followed by the one from Aubin et al. [25] and Noh and Kim [17] includes both a variable thickness model and a variable nucleation threshold. Using these considerations, the thermal performance of the PHP was accurately predicted. Most of the models are based on a 1-D discretization, however despite the increase in complexity and computational cost, some studies successfully performed 2D simulation of pulsating heat pipes [26,27].

The present work is part of the ongoing PHP2 EU CleanSky project, with the objective of developing PHPs for cooling applications of electronics onboard commercial aircraft. In particular, this means to fabricate and test PHPs experimentally at Provides Metalmeccanica and to upgrade and validate JJ Cooling Innovation's

numerical 1-D transient PHP design code. In the first part, the improvements on the numerical model are presented. Specifically, a new implementation of the initial film thickness as well as an improved solution to integrate nucleation in the model. These modifications greatly improved the accuracy and the stability of the code with respect to its previous version and permitted the simulation of higher-pressure fluids like R1233zd(E). The experimental setup used to test the first prototype of the PHP2 project is described subsequently. The numerical results obtained with R1223zd(E) at 70% filling ratio and 20°C coolant temperature for both vertical and horizontal orientation are shown. Finally, a quantitative validation of the numerical code is performed.

2. Numerical model improvements

The PHP numerical model presented here is a continuation of the studies from D'Entremont and Thome [28,29] and Aubin *et al.* [25,30,31]. It is a mechanistic 1D model based on a non-homogeneous approach where the fluid is represented as a sequence of liquid slugs and vapor plugs. The entire PHP loop is discretized into elements of the same size which contain a wall, liquid, liquid film and vapor. An element located in a liquid slug will only have a liquid component, an element located in a vapor plug will have both vapor and liquid film components, while an element including a bubble interface within it will have both liquid and vapor components (Fig. 1).

For the liquid slugs, single-phase convective heat transfer with the wall is considered, the liquid is assumed to be incompressible and the heat transfer at the interface with a plug (meniscus) is neglected. The film evaporation and condensation in the vapor plug is also modeled. The film thickness is considered uniform in each element and the initial thickness at the leading edge is dependent on the local fluid properties. Finally, the nucleation and coalescence of vapor plugs are also taken into account based on local conditions. It is worth mentioning that, in the exception of the modification presented here, all the conservation equations, constitutive relation and correlations remain unchanged from the model presented by Aubin *et al.* [25].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the control volumes [25,30].

Two main phenomena are driving the PHP performances. The first is the liquid film evaporation and condensation and the second the nucleation of new vapor plugs, which is characterized by a frequency of bubbles formation dependent on geometrical and thermal parameters. The magnitude of each of these phenomena will define the thermal-hydraulic performance of the PHP and might change with the working fluid type and/or the PHP geometry. Thus, the improvements in the simulation code were mainly focused on the mechanistic models of these phenomena and consequently targeting better thermal-hydraulic characterization of the PHP.

2.1 Liquid film thermal resistance

In previous studies [17,24,25], the linear heat flux at the inner channel wall and the local equivalent thermal resistances per unit of channel length for wall and liquid film were determined respectively by:

$$q'_{w-f} = \frac{1}{R'_{eq}} (T_w - T_v) \quad (1)$$

$$R'_{eq} = \frac{1}{2} R'_w + R'_f \quad (2)$$

where T_w , T_v , R'_w and R'_f , are the wall temperature, the vapor plug saturation temperature, the wall thermal resistance per unit of length and the film thermal resistance per unit of length, respectively. R'_{eq} is the equivalent

thermal resistance per unit of length from the vapor plug to the wall. It is important to mention that the wall temperature T_w is considered at $R'_w/2$.

The film and wall thermal resistance per unit of length are defined as:

$$R'_w = \frac{t_w}{k_w p_i} \quad (3)$$

$$R'_f = \frac{\delta}{k_l p_i} \quad (4)$$

where t_w , k_w , p_i , δ , k_l are respectively the tube wall thickness, the wall thermal conductivity, the internal perimeter, the film thickness, the liquid thermal conductivity. In Eq. 4, the liquid film thermal resistance was for a thin flat plate for which the cross-sectional area was expressed as:

$$A_{f,cs} = p_i \cdot \delta = \frac{m_{f'}}{\rho_f} \quad (5)$$

where m_{f}' and ρ_f are the mass of fluid in the film per unit of length and the density of the liquid film. This assumption is valid only if the liquid film is thin enough, which is not always the case in circular channels.

Thus, to obtain a rigorous solution, the film thickness is better modeled as a hollow cylinder as shown in Fig. 2. The film cross sectional area and its thermal resistance are then calculated using the radial conduction equation [32]. The wall and film equivalent thermal resistances are determined through Eqs. 6 and 7, and finally Eq. 8 for the film cross-sectional area.

$$R'_w = \frac{\ln(D_o/D_i)}{2\pi \cdot k_w} \quad (6)$$

$$R'_f = -\frac{\ln(1-(2\delta)/D_i)}{2\pi \cdot k_l} \quad (7)$$

$$A_{f,cs} = \pi(D_i - \delta) \cdot \delta = \frac{m_{f'}}{\rho_f} \quad (8)$$

where D_o and D_i are the outer and inner tube diameter.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the slab (left) and hollow cylinder (right) model for the film thermal resistance calculation.

Fig. 3 shows the relative error when using Eqs. 3 to 5 instead of the hollow cylinder expressions (Eqs. 6 to 8).

Fig. 3. Relative error on the liquid film cross-sectional area $A_{f,cs}$ and on the film thermal resistance R_f' (thin flat plate versus hollow cylinder).

2.2 Liquid film thickness

The PHP is physically characterized by the presence of vapor plugs and liquid slugs in a chaotic movement (pulsation) going forward and backward. During this movement, after the passage of a liquid slug, a liquid film is laid on the wall behind it (Fig. 1), the initial film thickness depends on certain flow characteristics. Aubin *et al.* [25] considered the empirical liquid film thickness correlation proposed by Moriyama and Inoue [33] and modified by Thome *et al.* [34] with an asymptotic expression to obtain a continuous relation over the whole range of conditions:

$$\frac{\delta_0}{D_i} = 3^{0.84} Re^{-0.42} [(0.07 Bo^{0.41})^{-8} + 0.1^{-8}]^{-1/8} \quad (9)$$

where, Re is the Reynolds number based on the velocity of the bubble leading meniscus and Bo is a modified Bond number [34], defined as:

$$Bo = \frac{\rho_l D_i U^2}{\sigma} \quad (10)$$

where, ρ_l , U and σ are respectively the liquid density, the velocity of the bubble and the surface tension.

In the present study, the initial liquid film thickness is modified considering the updated *Three-Zone model* proposed by Magnini *et al.* [35]. This model considers the use of three specific correlations that take into account different phenomena, which are linked to the following parameters: the meniscus velocity, its acceleration and the leading slug length.

Several correlations have been developed to estimate the film thickness of elongated bubbles assuming a steady isothermal flow. Han and Sihkazono [36] have shown that the bubble acceleration induces a reduction of the viscous boundary layer in the liquid slug, which decreases the initial film thickness when compared to the steady flow. Eqs. 11 and 12 incorporate the corrections from the study of Youn *et al.* [37] accurately validating the correlation on a larger Ca range:

$$\left(\frac{\delta_0}{D_i}\right)_{Steady} = \frac{0.67 Ca^{2/3}}{1 + 3.63 Ca^{2/3} + 0.534 Ca^{0.672} Re^{0.589} - 0.352 (Ca Re)^{0.640}} \quad (11)$$

$$\left(\frac{\delta_0}{D_i}\right)_{Accel.} = \frac{0.968 Ca^{2/3} Bo_a^{-0.414}}{1+4.83 Ca^{2/3} Bo_a^{-0.414}} \quad (12)$$

where, Ca is the capillary number and Bo_a is the Bond number related to the bubble meniscus acceleration, calculated as:

$$Ca = \frac{\mu_l U}{\sigma} \quad (13)$$

$$Bo_a = \frac{\rho_l a D_i^2}{\sigma} \quad (14)$$

where, μ_l is the liquid dynamic viscosity, and a is the bubble acceleration.

Eq. 11 was developed for laminar flow conditions when $Re < 2000$. When $Re \geq 2000$, Han and Shikazono proposed to evaluate the film thickness considering $Re = 2000$ in Eq. 11 and replacing in the same equation Ca by:

$$Ca = \frac{2000 \mu_l^2}{\rho_l \sigma D_i} \quad (15)$$

Additionally, the correlation developed by Aussilous & Quéré [38], which is based on the leading slug length (Eq. 16) is considered. They showed that if bubbles are too close to each other, the liquid film thickness of a trailing bubble is reduced. This is due to the development of the viscous boundary layer at the rear of a leading bubble, which limits the development of the liquid film around the bubble. Consequently, if $\delta < \delta_{vbl}$ the initial film thickness is assumed to be equal to the viscous boundary layer δ_{vbl} expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\delta_{vbl}}{D_i} = \left(\frac{L_l}{D_i} \frac{1}{Re}\right)^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

where L_l is the length of the leading slug.

Finally, the initial film thickness at the bubble nose is determined as follows:

$$\frac{\delta_0}{D_i} = \min \left[\left(\frac{\delta_0}{D_i}\right)_{Steady}, \left(\frac{\delta_0}{D_i}\right)_{Accel.}, \frac{\delta_{vbl}}{D_i} \right] \quad (17)$$

2.3 Vapor plugs generation

The PHP pulsating flow can be so intense that liquid slugs can reach the evaporator zone. If the wall superheat (the temperature difference between the inner wall and the liquid slug's saturation temperature) is higher than the nucleation threshold, a new vapor plug is generated. In the first version of the code, as well as in previous study [23], the nucleation threshold was a constant and predefined value and, consequently, a non-physical parameter, to eliminate this strong assumption, the nucleation threshold was determined using a well consolidated onset of pool boiling nucleation correlation and the wall roughness. This change was previously validated considering the experimental data of Jun and Kim [5], with ethanol as the working fluid [30,31]. However, as can be seen in Fig. 4, the difference in nucleation threshold can reach an order of magnitude of difference when comparing ethanol with R1233zd(E) as working fluid. Thus, for the same heat flux, the nucleation rate is expected to be much lower for PHPs with low pressure fluids (ethanol, methanol, water) than the ones with high pressure refrigerants (R134a, R1233zd(E), R1234ze(E)).

Yoon and Kim [12,39] have done a complete experimental and numerical analysis with a flat plate PHP using ethanol without including nucleation and not surprisingly obtained excellent results. It can lead one to the conclusion that the nucleation thermal effect is negligible when using low pressure working fluids. On the other

hand, for higher pressure working fluids and low surface roughness, the nucleation rate is expected to be high, and thus affecting the PHP pulsating intensity.

It is also worth to mention that in the previous version of the simulation code [25], as well as in the study of Noh and Kim [17], the size of the generated bubble was considered equal to the diameter of the channel. This is actually considered a strong assumption, since the density ratio of working fluids can be considerably different when comparing low with high saturation pressure fluids (Table 1). Unrealistic results with low predictability of the thermal performance were observed when considering such assumptions for working fluids with higher values of saturation pressure. Additionally, even if the nucleation phenomenon is faster for higher pressure working fluids, the elapsed time from the onset of nucleation threshold to the growing and departure of the bubble (for which it is assumed a channel-size bubble) is not negligible. The nucleation of a channel-size bubble during one timestep can cause severe instabilities in the code due to the surrounding heat and mass needed for the bubble generation. A solution could be to reduce the size of the bubble during its generation, but it would result in a very small discretized domain and thus will significantly increase the simulation time.

Fig. 4. Nucleation threshold as a function of saturation temperature for ethanol and R1233zd(E) with different cavity radius.

Table 1. Fluid properties at $T_{sat} = 25^{\circ}C$ and $T_{sat} = 50^{\circ}C$.

	$T_w = 25^{\circ}C$					$T_w = 50^{\circ}C$				
	P_{sat} [bar]	ρ_l/ρ_v [-]	μ_l [$\mu Pa \cdot s$]	σ [mN/m]	i_{lv} [kJ/kg]	P_{sat} [bar]	ρ_l/ρ_v [-]	μ_l [$\mu Pa \cdot s$]	σ [mN/m]	i_{lv} [kJ/kg]
Ethanol	0.08	5327	1082	22	921	0.29	1492	688	20	891
R1233zd(E)	1.3	175	286	15	191	2.9	77	225	11	177
R1234ze(E)	5.0	44	191	9	167	10.0	20	139	6	146
R1234yf	6.8	29	153	6	145	13.0	13	112	3	122

In the present study, the bubble formation in the several liquid slugs is better predicted. The subcooled nucleate boiling is predicted using the pool boiling correlation of Gorenflo [40], as proposed by Bae et al. [24]. h_{nb} is then used to calculate and store in a fictitious buffer, the amount of microbubbles generated in the corresponding liquid slug. At each time step, if the sum of the accumulated microbubbles in a slug is enough to generate a channel-size bubble and the nucleation superheat threshold is reached, then a new vapor plug is created at the maximum superheat location.

The pool boiling heat transfer coefficient is calculated using Eqs. 18 and 19 [40]. It includes the effect of the heat flux and pressure, working fluid properties, surface roughness and material of the heated wall.

$$h_{nb} = \begin{cases} 0 & , (T_w \leq T_{sat}) \\ h_{0,ref} F_{PR} \left(\frac{q_{nb}}{q_0}\right)^n \left(\frac{p_f}{p_{f,ref}}\right)^{0.6} \left(\frac{R_a}{R_{a,0}}\right)^{2/15} \left[\frac{(k\rho c)_w}{(k\rho c)_{Cu}}\right]^{1/4} & , (T_w > T_{sat}) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

$$q_{nb} = h_{nb}(T_w - T_{sat}) \quad (19)$$

Here, p_f is a working fluid property ratio defined as

$$p_f = \frac{(\partial P / \partial T)_{sat}}{\sigma} \quad (20)$$

Except for water, the pressure correction factor F_{PR} and the exponent n are expressed as :

$$F_{PR} = 0.7 p^{*0.2} + 4 p^* + (1.4 p^*) / (1 - p^*) \quad (21)$$

$$n = 0.95 - 0.3 p^{*0.3} \quad (22)$$

where p^* is the reduced pressure.

The measured reference values of $h_{0,ref}$, q_0 , $R_{a,0}$, p_f are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Reference values measured at $p_0^* = 0.1$ from Gorenflo [40].

$h_{0,ref}$	3580 W/m ² K
q_0	20 kW/m ²
$R_{a,0}$	0.4 μm
$p_{f,ref}$	1 (μm K) ⁻¹

3. Experimental test section

The prototype considered is the first of a series in the framework of the on-going EU project *PHP2*, which has been built by Provides Metalmeccanica S.r.l. The main objective is to generate a reliable experimental database to be able to validate the 1D numerical model. The relevant dimensions and parameters of the prototype *P1* are shown on the Table 3.

Table 3. Prototype 1 - Geometrical parameters.

Total PHP width, W [mm]	232
Evaporator length, L_a [mm]	19
Condenser length, L_c [mm]	58
Adiabatic length, L_a [mm]	111
Inner diameter, D_i [mm]	2
Outer diameter, D_o [mm]	4

Number of turns, [-]	19
Tube material	Copper
Surface roughness, Ra [μm]	0.5

The PHP is made of 2.0/4.0 mm ID/OD copper tubes brazed on the heat source on one side (evaporator zone) and on a heat sink on the other side (condenser zone). The critical diameter (Eq.22 for PHP is usually defined using the Bond number criteria $Bo = 4$). The curves of the critical diameter with R1233zdE as working fluid, assuming two different criterion $Bo = 4$ and $Bo = 1$, and for different saturation temperatures are shown on the Fig. 5. According to this criterion, Prototype 1 is at the limit of this criterion. However, several studies have shown better performance using a larger diameter PHP [41,42].

$$D_{i,crit} = 2 \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{(\rho_l - \rho_v)g}} \quad (22)$$

Fig. 5. Critical diameter for R1233zd(E), for $Bo = 4$ and $Bo = 1$.

The heat source is composed of a 2 mm copper plate on which 4 ceramic heaters are fixed. Four thermocouples were uniformly placed on the heat source surface 1 mm below the brazing point of the tube. To improve the thermal contact between thermocouples and the ceramic heaters, a commercial thermal paste is used, which has a thermal conductivity of 12.5 W/mK.

At the condenser side, like the evaporator, four thermocouples are uniformly located on the condenser surface, 1 mm below the brazing point of the tube. The condenser is cooled using a thermal bath with water at 20°C. Four additional thermocouples are located at the middle of the adiabatic section taped on the copper tube. Two of them are located on the 4th tube from the PHP left side, the other two on the 4th tube from the right side. Two pressure transducers are installed on the same loop at the middle of the adiabatic length (*cf.* Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 for an overall understanding). The operating conditions considered for this study are shown on the Table 4.

Table 4. Prototype 1 - Operating conditions.

Working fluid	R1233zd(E)
Orientation	Horizontal / Vertical

Filling ratio [%]	70
Coolant temperature [$^{\circ}C$]	20
Coolant flow rate [mL/min]	1450
Heat load [W]	up to 230W

Fig. 6. Experimental setup Prototype 1.

Fig. 7. Test set up in horizontal orientation not insulated yet.

The experimental temperature measurements were aggregated to simplify the comparison with the numerical results. The mean wall evaporator and condenser temperatures, $\bar{T}_{w,e}$ and $\bar{T}_{w,c}$ are determined with the arithmetic means of the 4 thermocouples measurements, in their respective PHP zones, during 200s after the steady or pseudo-steady state is reached. The PHP thermal resistance is calculated as:

$$R_{PHP} = \frac{\bar{T}_{w,e} - \bar{T}_{w,c}}{Q_e} \quad (24)$$

where, Q_e is the total heat applied on the evaporator zone.

The condenser equivalent thermal resistance per unit length is back-calculated using:

$$R'_{eq,c} = \frac{\bar{T}_{w,c} - \bar{T}_{cool}}{Q_e} L_{tot,c} \quad (25)$$

where, \bar{T}_{cool} is the mean temperature between condenser inlet and outlet, and $L_{tot,c}$ is the cumulative tube length in the condenser part of the PHP.

The whole setup is completely insulated to avoid heat losses. Leak tests were run to check on vacuum and pressure tightness and the test fluid was charged after evacuating the unit. All the thermocouples are K-type calibrated with a high accuracy Pt-100 probe. Uncertainty of all the sensors measurements and the power supply reading are summarized in Table 5. Following the uncertainty propagation method, the maximum relative error on the thermal resistance stays below 3%.

Table 5. Sensor uncertainty.

K-type thermocouples	0.1K
Power transducer	0.4% of the reading
Scale	0.3g
Pressure transducers	0.1% FS
Flow meter	2.8 mL/min
Inclinometer	0.2°

4. Numerical results and discussions

The input data considered for simulations are those presented in the previous section, geometry and operating conditions from Table 3 and Table 4, respectively. A uniform and constant heat flux is considered at the evaporator side. As the experimental test section was thermally insulated, no heat losses were considered. For each predicted operating condition, the solver runs 150s of real operating time to ensure that the PHP reaches a stable pulsation mode. The Courant number was optimized to reduce the computational time while keeping stability and accuracy of the simulation, which led to variable time steps in the order of 120 μ s. A mesh independency is presented on Fig. 8. For this study, the element size is set equal to the internal tube diameter (2mm). For each discretized element, all computed variables were saved every 0.05s of simulation time. The PHP temperature (wall and fluid) is initialized at $T_{init} = (\bar{T}_{w,e} + \bar{T}_{w,c})/2$, where $\bar{T}_{w,e}$ and $\bar{T}_{w,c}$ were taken from the experimental results. Similarly to the experimental data, the average wall temperature at the evaporator and condenser sides are used to calculate the predicted PHP thermal resistance.

Fig. 8. Mesh independency analysis on the element size.

4.1 Predicted PHP Visualization

To study the flow characteristics and heat transfer performance of the PHP, the numerical case for R1233zd(E), vertical orientation, 70% filling ratio and 200W of applied heat load is considered. The mean predicted temperatures of each zone of the PHP are shown on Fig. 9, where it can be seen that stable pulsating mode is reached after about 10s.

Fig. 9. Variation of the mean temperatures over time.

Fig. 10 shows the balance in terms of heat transferred at the condenser and evaporator along the time. For this specific simulated case, a small fluctuation is observed from the equilibrium after 10s of PHP operation. However, depending on the applied heat load, geometry of PHP, working fluid being considered and other several parameters, this unbalanced heat transfer fluctuations can be smaller or bigger. This is expected due to the chaotic pulsation of PHPs, which means different degrees of thermal inertia in the evaporator and condenser. However, the energy balance is respected along the time, proving that a reliable solver was developed.

Fig. 10. Net heat transfer rate over time.

Fig. 11 shows the average slug velocity in the middle of the condenser section of the second loop of the PHP over time. To be able to see the amplitude and period of the pulsations, data are exported in a 10 second window starting at $t = 75s$. The FFT analysis done over the 150s of simulation presented on Fig. 12 is showing that at 200W, the pulsation frequency is around 3.2 Hz.

Fig. 11. Local and PHP-Averaged slug velocity

Fig. 12. FFT analysis of the local bulk velocity in the adiabatic zone.

Fig. 13 shows the absolute mean value of the heat flux distribution over the 2nd loop of the PHP starting from the left side. The averaging is made after reaching the pulsating steady state mode, from 10s to 150s. As expected, the external heat flux is constant on the evaporator zone and null in the adiabatic zone. The symmetrical shape of the heat flux distribution at the condenser section is typical to a pulsation mode behavior. In average, the vapor plugs are pulsating equivalently from both upstream and downstream channels. Fig. 14 shows the average of all the liquid slugs' bulk velocity over the whole PHP versus time as well as the moving average in red. A value close to 0m/s would then mean that the PHP is in a perfectly symmetrical pulsation mode. A mean value of around -0.05 m/s is observed, which shows a slight preference for the downstream pulsation, but overall, the change of sign in the velocity plot is a clear indication of the pulsation mode of the PHP.

Fig. 13. Predicted local heat flux for the 2nd PHP loop.

Fig. 14. Average of all liquid slug's bulk velocity showing pulsation mode.

Fig. 15 shows an example of a simulated circulation mode PHP. In this case, it shows that all the vapor plugs are moving downstream (from the right side) and thus being condensed preferentially on one side. To confirm this assumption, Fig. 16 shows the average of the liquid slugs' bulk velocity over the time. A mean value of around -0.22 m/s is observed, with only slight oscillation and no change in the liquid slug direction (sign change) confirming the circulation mode and that the code is able to predict its occurrence.

Fig. 15. Example of a circulation mode behavior on the predicted local heat flux.

Fig. 16. Example of a circulation mode behavior on the predicted average liquid slug's bulk velocity.

4.2 Validation

The predicted local wall temperature profile of the 2nd PHP loop is shown in Fig. 17. The two red points on the figure correspond to the local thermocouples measurement placed on the adiabatic zone. It can be seen that the temperature gradient is well predicted by the numerical model.

Fig. 17. Predicted local wall temperature profile for the 2nd PHP loop versus experimental thermocouple measurements.

Fig. 18 and Fig. 19 show the comparison between predicted and experimental results of mean evaporator temperature, respectively, for vertical and horizontal PHP orientations. The evaluated range of heat load is from 20W to 230W for the vertical orientation and from 30W to 120W for the horizontal orientation. In general, reasonably accurate predictions are observed, with some overprediction in temperature only observed for high heat loads and under vertical orientation (conservative result when designing PHPs). This difference might come from the lack of 2D conduction at the evaporator side. Furthermore, Fig. 19 shows that the code even predicts the “step-change” in the experimental temperature at the lower heat duty.

Fig. 18. Predicted versus experimental mean evaporator wall temperature. P1, R1233zd(E), Vertical orientation, $T_{cool} = 20^{\circ}C$

Fig. 19. Predicted versus experimental mean evaporator wall temperature. P1, R1233zd(E), Horizontal orientation, $T_{cool} = 20^{\circ}C$.

Fig. 20 and Fig. 21 show the mean values of the PHP thermal resistance calculated using Eq. 24. The jump observed in the horizontal case is a change of PHP operating regime from short amplitude steady oscillations to a low frequency high amplitude oscillation (intermittent flow).

The mean absolute percentage error (MAE) and mean percentage error (ME) are summarized in Table 6. 88% of the data within 15% of relative error and 98% within 30%. Based on the observed results, it can be concluded that the PHP simulation tool is a reliable engineering solution for the prediction of the thermal performance and flow regimes of closed loop PHPs for vertical and horizontal orientations over the entire range of heat duties from low at onset of boiling/pulsation up to the highest tested. It has also been shown that the temperature profile along the length of the PHP was well predicted in the diabatic zone. Various trends in the data were also captured, including some chaotic and consequently unstable flow in PHPs as the flow regime changes.

Fig. 20. Predicted versus experimental mean PHP thermal resistance. P1, R1233zd(E), Vertical orientation, $T_{cool} = 20^{\circ}C$.

Fig. 21. Predicted versus experimental mean PHP thermal resistance. P1, R1233zd(E), Horizontal orientation, $T_{cool} = 20^{\circ}C$.

Table 6. Percentage error of the validation over the 49 datapoints.

Mean absolute percentage error (MAE)	7.7 %
Mean percentage error (ME)	2.1 %
Percentage of data within $\pm 15\%$	88 %
Percentage of data within $\pm 30\%$	98 %

5. Conclusion

Implementation of the film thermal resistance and film thickness based on a radial model was presented. The initial film thickness laid behind a liquid slug was updated to include dynamic effect of the bubble. A new method to implement vapor plug formation were also presented. These improvements made to the numerical model now permits to accurately simulate cases with low-GWP volatile working fluids. The numerical model is successfully validated for the first prototype of the PHP2 project with R1233zd(E) as working fluid, 70% filling ratio, 20°C coolant temperature for both vertical and horizontal orientation. The error on the prediction is less than 8% for all the presented datapoints. Moreover, the code proved its capability to accurately predict the local gradient of temperature as well as changes in flow regimes in horizontal orientation. The experimental campaign in the EU project PHP2 is ongoing for different working fluids and geometrical designs of PHPs. Thus, more validations on JJ Cooling Innovation's code are expected for the near future. Based on the validations shown here and previously in [30], this versatile code is becoming one of the most complete thermal design tool for PHPs. It allows one to design new PHP units, and compare competing geometrical configuration and operating conditions, to bring this emerging cooling technology into the mainstream of electronics cooling.

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